

THE ISSUE OF INTRODUCING AXIOLOGICAL APPROACHES THROUGH HISTORY TEACHING IN FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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The outstanding axiological potential of students is one of the types of personality potential. Like other types of human potential, it reflects the sum of innate and acquired abilities (resources, resources, and opportunities) to respond to the reality around a person and determines his or her possible response rate to socio-pedagogical conditions. A distinctive feature of axiological potential over other types of personality potential is its axiological basis, the essence of which can be revealed by the concepts of "value" and "value orientation". The category of "value" is one of the general scientific concepts that are especially important for pedagogy from a methodological point of view.

A study of the literature has given us reason to say that value is viewed in many senses and from different angles. The use of the concept of 'value' in the everyday sense is related to the subject's valuation activities and means something very important, important to the society or the individual. Understanding values as abstract objects and ideals are most commonly used.

The philosophical understanding of values is related to such characteristics as usefulness, importance, significance, normality, usefulness, which clearly define the scope of this concept. In the sociological literature, values do not diminish in importance as a basis, nor in norms and ideals. Value is any goal that is ideal and has a regulatory effect on subjective relationships. From a psychological point of view, values are the most important component of a personality and play a managerial and regulatory role in his or her life.

From a pedagogical point of view, a person's values are the internal, emotionally assimilated regulator of his or her activities that determines his or her relationship to the world around him or her, and to the nature of the activity being performed.

Accordingly, we consider values as the general meanings of life carried out by the person, they are the formative units of the person's consciousness and determine the person's moral position. In the scientific literature, special attention is paid to the issue of highlighting the most important values. This

issue is covered in detail in the works of I.K. Juravleva, V.A. Karakovskiy, A.V. Kiryakova, I. Ya. Lerner, Z.I. Ravkina, R.M. Rogovoy, N.S. Rozova, N.L. Khudyakova and e.t.c.

In terms of solving the problem of the role of values in the axiological potential structure, N.L. Xudyakova. We then follow the following typology of values: values of individual use, social significance, personal significance, and general meaningful species.

Values of the personal useful type are values that reflect a person's striving for defined forms of relationships at a specific level of representation that is defined through emotional evaluation as useful to meet life-level needs.

Values of the type of social significance are the values that determine the aspirations of individuals and social groups to normative forms of relationships that are recognized as necessary and sufficient (optimal) by the individual. Values of personal significance are the values that define a person's aspiration to forms of relationship with reality, which he considers necessary and sufficient about the personal interpretation of these concepts and categories, through which he expresses reality. The value of a species of general importance is a very universal value that characterizes a person's desire for a harmonious form of cultural mediation, which allows a person to fully realize his or her openness to the world and goes beyond his or her sustainable idealization. Value competition.

It is well known that a person's values are manifested in his or her value orientations, which reflect the integral unity of the leading interests of the individual and society. We come from the premise that value orientations are determined by the values of society and as a result are subject to constant change. The unity of the leading interests of the individual and society allows a person to determine the cultural parameters of his activities, as well as to regulate the direction of his activities. It should also be noted that value orientations reflect the set of values that are accepted and implemented by man; they act as socio-psychological formations that embody the goals, motives, attitudes, and several other ideological features of the individual.

In other words, value orientations are an integral part of a person's socio-psychological structure, it is a system of values that reflects his or her life and professional goals, is the most important and personal meaning for him or her, and determines his or her behavior. attitude to the surrounding reality.

In our definition of the concept of "axiological potential of the individual", we take into account the following:

1) the potential of the person - is a set of resources, reserves, and capabilities of the person; at the same time, resources describe potential in terms of the past, reserves reflect current potential, and opportunities reflect future-oriented;

2) axiology - the doctrine of the nature of values, the place and role of people's worldview and worldview in the overall structure;

3) The diversity of values can be presented in the form of the following types: individual useful, socially significant, personally significant, and general in meaning.

As a result, the axiological potential of a student's personality can be defined as an integrated personal education characterized by a hierarchy of stable value orientations that determine the knowledge, understanding, and acceptance of the values of the professional community.

Abydenova, G.N. Levashova, G.A. Melekesova, O.O. Nenasheva, and A.A. According to Polyakova, the following components can be distinguished in the axiological potential of students: cognitive-semantic, emotional-volitional, motivational-activity and reflexive-evaluation. Each of the components is delivered following the specifications:

- cognitive-semantic: presentation and understanding of the essence of value directions; understanding the meaning of value orientations and understanding them as personal values; understanding the need to act following values of social and professional significance;

- emotionally strong will: emotional stability, overcoming difficulties on an emotionally positive level; voluntary regulation of behavior, the formation of volitional qualities (discipline, independence, perseverance, endurance, organization, perseverance, and initiative);

- Motivational Activity: the pursuit of behavior by generally accepted values; motivation to expand their knowledge of society and the values of the professional community; ability to make independent choices in life and professional situations;

- the ability to communicate between their actions and the values of society and the professional community; the ability to adequately evaluate one's behavior and the behavior of other people in terms of value. Hence, the axiological potential reflects the aggregate.

The organization of axiological activity is the reconstruction of students with the personalization and dramatization of historical events, to form a personal emotional-value relationship using a set of methodological methods,

such as working from different perspectives, assessment, and documentation, project creation, modeling of various situations with staging in an ethical selection environment, educational communication, and commentary.

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